

Quality of Life among Diabetic Patients Type II in PHCs, Taif City, Saudi Arabia

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Abstract

In view of the growing number of type II diabetes patients in general, and particularly in Saudi Arabia, it was critical to analyze the quality of life for diabetic patients in Taif city as a first step toward finding solutions to prevent the condition from recurring. Diabetic patients' lives are sadly influenced negatively, both physiologically and psychologically, resulting in despair for the patient and his family.

Methods: 385 diabetic patients in Taif City, Saudi Arabia, participated in a cross-sectional study between November 2023 and November 2024. using the DQoL questionnaire in its approved Arabic version. Using the independent sample t-test and one-way ANOVA, sociodemographic information and clinical investigations, such as HbA1c and BMI, were sought in order to investigate the impact of these factors on the quality of life of diabetes patients. Study had an Institutional Review Board Approval letter number 2023-698.

Results: Particularly among older persons, the majority of patients had Type 2 Diabetes (96.6% vs. 0.8% for Type 1), which is in line with worldwide trends. Three-quarters of participants have had type 2 diabetes for less than 20 years, whereas a sizable portion (19.7%) have managed the disease for 20 to 29 years, and 4.2% have had it for 30 to 39 years. A family history of diabetes was present in 87.3% of the population. Patients are happy with their care, food, social interactions, blood sugar checks, testing, and overall quality of life. They are worried about comorbidities, future emergencies, body shape, and loss of consciousness, though.

Conclusion: Research and treatment for type 2 diabetes must be prioritized. The need of attending to the needs of both newly diagnosed patients and those with long-term diabetes cannot be overstated. Community education and preventative initiatives could also greatly reduce the future prevalence of diabetes by taking advantage of the high frequency of family history.

More Information

How to cite this article: Alosaimi JA, Algethami AKR, Alotaibi EM, Alsulaimani NH, Kofi M. Quality of Life among Diabetic Patients Type II in PHCs, Taif City, Saudi Arabia. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(1):193-202.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).28

Keywords:

Type II Diabetes Mellitus,
Quality of Life,
Saudi Arabia.

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Introduction

Type II diabetes mellitus (DM) is one of the most common chronic diseases that spreads throughout the world. Sadly, the number of diabetic patients has rapidly increased. While many health organizations are working to find an effective treatment, other organizations are barely making any headway in reducing the number of patients. By 2030, it is predicted that there will be 783 million people with Type II diabetes. Many studies have demonstrated that the MENA Region—Middle East and North Africa—has the highest prevalence of type II diabetes worldwide. About 18% of people are between the ages of 20 and 79. By 2045, it is anticipated to reach 20% [1].

Researchers have conducted numerous studies to understand how T2DM affects patients' quality of life and the factors that influence it. Older patients and those with concomitant complications such as peripheral neuropathy, stroke, nephropathy, arthritis, and insulin treatment are common factors that impact the quality of life for people with type 2 diabetes [2]. According to other research, patients with different chronic complications have a lower quality of life, particularly as the number and severity of these complications increase [3-5]. In fact, compared to other physiological factors like HbA1C, which are typically used to evaluate the health status of diabetic patients, psycho-social factors for these patients exhibit better predictors of pertinent clinical outcomes like mortality and hospitalization [6,7].

According to other studies, women with diabetes had a significantly lower health-related quality of life (HRQOL) than men did, and their diabetes had a greater influence on their day-to-day lives [8-10].

Diabetes patients' ages were also considered; study demonstrated that older patients, regardless of gender, have lower HRQoL mean scores [11-13]. Patients who are young, male, have a higher socioeconomic standing, are working, and have better health outcomes than women.

A cross-sectional study conducted in King Abdulaziz University about Quality of life, stress, anxiety and depression and associated factors among people with type 2 diabetes mellitus in Western region Saudi Arabia, the study concluded that depression, anxiety, and stress were common in T2DM patients. Thus, all these factors should be considered when monitoring T2DM patients [14].

A different study found that patients who have a high level of education and stable employment have a higher quality of life than those who are unemployed and uneducated [15]. HRQOL scores were significantly lower for those without employment than for those with a low level of education, as documented by additional researches.

Diabetes duration has a significant detrimental effect on quality of life [16]. According to two studies, having diabetes mellitus-related complications, particularly serious ones, was linked to lower HRQOL scores. In patients with type-2 DM, preventing complications has the biggest impact on improving health-related quality of life [17,18]. Patients with type 2 diabetes (T2DM) have a lower quality of life (QoL) than people in general [19].

The International Diabetes Federation (idf.org) reported that in Saudi Arabia, 4,274,100 adult cases of diabetes, representing a 17.7% prevalence of the disease. Both micro and macrovascular defects, including diabetic foot, retinopathy, nephropathy, CVA, and CVD, can be brought on by diabetes mellitus and its complications. The quality of life for patients whose percentage is rising yearly was called into question by these facts. The cost of medical care for diabetic patients is ten times higher than that of non-diabetic patients, according to a study that reviewed the literature on the quality of life of diabetic patients in Saudi Arabia, that money is spent on medication, home care, surgery, medical care, and follow-up. Each patient has a different quality of life based on their social, psychological, physical, and financial circumstances [20]. The financial condition has a significant impact on improving the quality of life for diabetic patients [21]. In this study our aim is to assess the quality of life of patients with type II diabetes in Diabetes and Endocrine Specialist Center (DESC) at Prince Mansour Military Hospital, Taif city, Saudi Arabia, and to measure the outcome factors such as complications, and metabolic factors, using the validated Arabic version of (DQoL) questionnaire.

Method

Between January and December 2024, a cross-sectional descriptive study was carried out at the Diabetic and Endocrine Specialist Center at Prince Mansour Military Hospital in Taif City, Saudi Arabia. Male and female adults with Type II diabetes who are between the ages of 20 and 80 make up the study population. Patients who receive daily, routine follow-up visits are study participants. Exclusions from the study include patients who are pregnant, under the age of 18, have physical or mental disabilities, have serious or advanced complications, or decline to participate.

Using a stratified random sampling technique with equal allocation, 385 participants were chosen from the Diabetic Endocrine Specialist Center (DESC) clinics to make up the estimated sample size, which has a 5% error, a 95% confidence level, a power of 0.8, and an expected response distribution of 0.5.

The validated Arabic version of the Diabetes Quality of Life questionnaire, a highly effective and dependable instrument for assessing type II diabetic patients, was utilized as the data collection tool in this study.

Numerous languages have translated it, and Jordan is where the Arabic version first appeared [22]. This survey is suitable for use in Arabic-speaking nations. In Saudi Arabia, we made the decision to use it. It is divided into four major sections. Demographic information and the patient's medical history—including treatment, coexisting conditions and complications, BMI, and test results—are covered in the first section.

The patient's satisfaction with the treatment plan, test time, diet, family load, disease education, sleep, social interactions, school and home activities, body, sport, and leisure time, and, lastly, overall satisfaction are all questioned in the second section. The impact of diabetes mellitus on patients is addressed in the third section, which begins with pain, embarrassment, fatigue, self-satisfaction, driving, social interactions related to the disease, and food type. Concerns about diabetes are covered in the fourth section. concerns about living a normal life, losing consciousness, changing physically, and potential problems in the future.

A 5-point Likert scale was used for satisfaction questions, where 1 meant "very satisfied" and 5 meant "totally unsatisfied." The Likert scale is also used for questions about impact and worry, with answers ranging from "not at all" (one point) to "always" (five points). Information regarding medications was also gathered from medical records. Yes = 1 / No = 2 is the binary mean score for treatment and related chronic illnesses. A higher binary scale indicates a better state of health.

Statistical Analysis

Version 28 of the statistical package of social sciences (SPSS) was used to analyze the data. Every variable is subjected to descriptive statistics. For qualitative variables, proportion and frequency; for quantitative variables, mean and standard deviation. The Chi Square test for qualitative variables and the t-test for quantitative variables are two examples of analytical statistics in action. A P-value of less than 0.05 and a 95% confidence interval are considered statistically significant.

All of the satisfaction, impact, and worry scores were added up to create a grand measure score that varied from 4 to 20 for worry, 11 to 55 for impact, and 14 to 70 for satisfaction. A score ranging from 1 to 5 was calculated by dividing the grand measure score by the total number of items; a lower score indicated a higher quality of life (QoL). The descriptive data were expressed as mean±standard deviation, frequency, median, and range. One way analysis of variance (Anova) and unpaired t-test were the key statistical tests used in this study. The level for significance was $p > 0.05$ for all tests to evaluate the influence of patients'

sociodemographic and medical characteristics on their quality of life.

All participants gave their verbal informed consent, and the study was approved by the authorized IRB. Information about patients is kept private.

Ethical Considerations: Data collected used for the purpose of this research only. Consent for survey were collected ahead of completing the survey. Participation was voluntary. Study had an Institutional Review Board Approval letter number 2023-698.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 displays the sociodemographic and clinical attributes of the research participants. The study's focus on a demographic that is closely associated with retirement or chronic illnesses suggests that the sample is primarily older, with 66.2% of the group being between the ages of 50 and 69.

Table 1: Socio-Demographic Data of the Study Participants(n=385)

Personnel information	Percent	
Gender	Male	44.9
	Female	54.8
	Total	99.7
Age	20-39	3.1
	40-49	11.2
	50-59	35.8
	60-69	30.4
	70-79	13.2
	over 80	4.2
Occupation	Teacher /Employee	3.4
	Housewife	51.2
	Military	12.2
	Other	1.0
	Retired	31.9
Marital Status	Married	92.5
	Divorced	1.0
	Widowed	4.7
Education	Illiterate	8.6
	elementary	4.7
	Preparatory	2.9
	Secondary	76.9
	Undergraduate	.8
	Postgraduate	4.2
Smoking status	Smoker	7.0
	Non-smoker	88.8
	Negative smoker	3.4
Residency	City	84.2
	Rural	9.6
Average income	Less than 1000SR	9.1
	1001-10000	73.8
	over 10000	16.1

33.8% are younger age groups (20–39). Retirees and housewives make up a sizable portion of the workforce

(51.2% and 31.9% respectively). Armed forces personnel make up 12.2% of the workforce. The fact that 92.5% of the participants were married raises cultural norms in this society.

The age range of participants in this study is 50-69 years old, with the majority being retirees and housewives, which weakens the employment aspect when analyzing the quality of life for this segment of society. On the other hand, the majority of this layer is married, which improves quality of life metrics because patients are generally healthier than those who live alone.

Nearly three thirds of the respondents have finished secondary education 76.9%, while only 4.2 % have their bachelor degree. 0.8% having completed postgraduate studies. This suggests a high rate of illiteracy of 8.6%, which may be relevant to our evaluation of the quality of life of patients with type 2 diabetes.

Unfortunately, three-thirds of the participants have only completed high school, which is due to societal conventions, as university degrees were not widely available at the time, and society prefers that women marry rather than study. That may indicate a high rate of illiteracy, which necessitates the implementation of health education and awareness plans, as well as methods for dealing with chronic diseases such as diabetes, through home visits and awareness campaigns in health centers such as Diabetes and Endocrinology Specialist Centers.

Even while the tiny fraction of smokers (7.0%) and passive smokers (3.4%) should be prioritized when developing efforts to enhance the health of specific areas, the fact that 88.8% of participants do not smoke should give public health advocates hope. This layer requires further investigation to determine the causes for the predisposition toward health activities despite the high illiteracy rate.

The urban-rural mix is disproportionately composed of city dwellers (84.2%); this may be due to regional demographic trends. The group exhibits some economic variance mostly; a majority (73.8%) falls in the middle-income range while a smaller percentage at the extremes of the income distribution.

In general, the sample represents a middle-class, older, married city inhabitant with significant educational inequalities and a strong desire to avoid smoking. Living in the metropolis has enabled those patients to cope with their conditions. The availability of free and semi-free medical care and medicine greatly aided disease control and reduced mortality rates.

According to this study, the majority of patients who visit DESC for follow-up had Type 2 Diabetes (96.6% vs. 0.8% for Type 1), which is consistent with global trends, especially among older adults. Three thirds of the participants are having type 2 Diabetes duration for less than 20 years, Which indicates that they are accustomed to control the disease. Furthermore, a

good number (19.7%) have coped with diabetes for 20 to 29 years, which emphasizes the need of programs and tools created especially to handle the long-term treatment of the condition. The tiny fraction of individuals with diabetes (4.2%) who have had it for 30-39 years or more emphasizes how urgently enhanced and thorough treatment is needed for this population. Both trends in survival and advancements in treatment are reflected in this minority.

In particular, 87.3% of people had a family history of diabetes, which is a fairly high percentage. This emphasizes the necessity of both genetic predisposition and common environmental or lifestyle factors in the onset of diabetes in a population. Families are vital, and with an eye toward the younger generations who are more susceptible, there is a chance to teach them the importance of making informed decisions and taking preventative measures.

Table 2: Diabetes History and Duration (n=385)

		Percent
Diabetes	type 1	.8
	type 2	96.6
Duration of diabetes	0-19	75.8
	20-29	19.7
	30-39	4.2
	40 years and over	.3
Family history of diabetes	yes	87.3
	no	5.5

Treatment

Information about diabetics' dietary habits and medication usage reveals important trends and potential areas for diabetes treatment advancement.

Table 3: Dietary Habits and Medication Usage

Treatment	Percentage
Dietary Plan Yes	6.2
No	76.4
Insulin	31.2
Basal insulin	36.9
Bolus Insulin	23.4
Mixed Insulin	3.1
Metformin	83.1
Sulphonylurea	38.2
SGLT-2 Inhibitors	49.9
DPP4	36.6
GLP1 Receptor agonist	13.0
Bioglitazone	8.1
ACEinhibitors	29.1
ARBS	21.0
CCB	18.7
Betablockers	2.6
Antiplatelet	30.1
Statins	89.6

With only 6.2% of participants actively adhering to a recommended diet, we require more education and assistance to increase dietary adherence. Additionally, a low utilization rate is demonstrated, with only 31.2% of diabetic patients using insulin. Due to its primary use in the treatment of severe disorders, bolus insulin is used less frequently (23.4% of users) and mixed insulin is used less frequently (3.1% of users), even though the majority of users (26.5%) have been on basal insulin for 0–19 years. The fact that 83.1% of participants are dependent on metformin further supports the medication's fundamental role in the treatment of type 2 diabetes. As the GLP-1 receptor.

Additionally, the use of cardiovascular and renal protective drugs, such as statins (89.6%), angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors (ACEs) (29.1%), and angiotensin receptor blockers (ARBs), is indicative of the treatment of concomitant diseases. Antiplatelet medications (30.1%) and beta blockers (2.6%) are also used to reduce the cardiovascular risks associated with diabetes.

According to the statistics, the majority of medications are prescribed to patients whose duration of diabetes

ranged from less than a year, to 19 years. This highlights the importance of regularly checking for side effects and adhering to a medication schedule over the long term. The results highlight the necessity of dietary guidance, promoting the proper use of insulin and contemporary drugs, and combining treatment for related conditions in order to effectively manage diabetes.

Comorbidities

Diabetes treatment must be approached holistically because the disease can cause serious health problems. 8.3% of participants have retinopathy, a common eye condition associated with diabetes. This suggests that this condition is less common in this group than in others, despite the fact that it is still a significant problem.

However, hypertension is present in nearly half of the patients 51.4%, highlighting the significant risk factors that cardiovascular disease and renal impairment represent. This makes it very clear that the best way to manage high blood pressure and diabetes is to receive coordinated treatment.

Figure1: Comorbidities

Diabetics have a higher risk of cardiovascular diseases, as evidenced by the 8.8% prevalence of cardiovascular disorders in the general population. Accordingly, 1.0% of people reported cerebral blood vessel abnormalities, including stroke. This is a lower but still concerning number considering the seriousness of the potential consequences. The fact that 8.1% of participants experienced issues related to nephrology highlights the prevalence of kidney diseases and highlights the necessity of routinely monitoring and managing renal health in individuals with diabetes.

Further evidence of the various health problems people with diabetes face comes from the fact that 10.9% of participants report having other diseases, most likely associated with a range of metabolic, autoimmune, or

secondary disorders. In order to improve overall results, it is crucial to manage both current problems and associated comorbidities with diabetes through a multidisciplinary approach. These outcomes support this strategy.

Body Measurements

Measurements of the body revealed the following statistical findings. Seven of the 378 participants had information that was overlooked. The sample range in weight from 40.7 kg to 145.0 kg. This group's body weight variance is fairly modest, with a mean of 80.29 kg and a standard deviation of 15.27 kg. The height range in the same sample is 117–194 cm. Height varies somewhat moderately, according to the mean height of 159.89 cm and the standard deviation of 9.47 cm.

Table 4: Body Measurements

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean±SD
Body weight	378	40.7	145.0	80.286±15.2
Height	378	117.00	194.00	159.8929±9.4
BMI	370	12.6	63.9	31.328±5.8

The body mass index (BMI) of participants in the data set ranged from 12.6 to 63.9.

Standard deviations of the body mass index (BMI) range from 31.33 to 5.89. The fact that the mean body mass index is higher than the typical range of 18.5-24.9 suggests that the majority of participants are most likely overweight or obese, which may be related to societal lifestyle choices.

These statistical analysis reveal a wide spectrum of values, implying that body composition varies and could be areas where health management could be strengthened especially in relation to BMI and related risks.

Laboratory Tests

372 participants' cholesterol levels varied greatly, ranging from 1.5 to 9.6. The mean cholesterol level was 4.45, and the standard deviation was 1.12. With an average of 2.99 and a standard deviation of 7.8, the 365 people whose LDL levels were examined had values ranging from 0.70 to 151,000. The high standard deviation suggests that there is some variation in the LDL levels in the sample. Among the 368 participants, triglycerides, or TG, ranged from 0.50 to 14.90, with a mean of 1.60 and a standard deviation of 1.1. Despite the large range shown here, most people have smaller amounts.

Table 5: Laboratory Tests

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean±SD
Cholestrol	372	1.5	9.6	4.446±1.12
LDL	365	.70	151.00	2.9914±7.8
TG	368	.50	14.90	1.5960±1.12
CREATININE	373	1.1	345.0	76.542±31
ACR	370	.00	524.00	13.3884±50
eGFR	363	.6	121.0	87.476±21.1
MAU	374	5.0	4061.0	78.175±292
HbA1C	379	4.90	127.00	12.1621±16.1
FBS	345	3.5	350.0	127.881±53.4
RBS	323	22.2	500.0	198.497±56

The creatinine levels of 373 individuals ranged from 1.1 to 345.0, with a mean of 76.54 and a standard deviation of 31. The large range and high standard deviation suggest that there is some variation in the kidney function of the sample. With a mean of 13.39 and a standard deviation of 50, the albumin-to-creation ratios (ACR) of 370 subjects ranged from 0.00 to 524.00, indicating a broad range of albumin levels.

The estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) of the 363 participants in the study ranged from 0.6 to 121.0, with a mean value of 87.48 and a standard deviation of 21.1. The results show that there is a moderate variation in the individuals' renal filtration rates. In all, 374 subjects had microalbuminuria (MAU) values ranging from 5.0 to 4061.0. The mean MAU level was 78.18, and the standard deviation was 292. This wide range of data suggests that some people may excrete a lot of albumin.

The hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c) ranges for the 379 participants are 4.90 to 127.00, with a mean of 12.16 and a standard deviation of 16.1. There is a great deal of variation here, which would imply that some of the

participants are not managing their diabetes. The fasting blood sugar (FBS) of the 345 subjects varies slightly, with a mean of 127.88 and a standard deviation of 53.4.

Nonetheless, the majority of people might have elevated blood sugar levels. The results show that blood sugar levels vary widely; some of the 323 participants have notable peaks, with random blood sugar levels ranging from 22.2 to 500.0. The mean value is 198.50, with a standard deviation of 56. This cohort appears to have a broad range of metabolic and renal functions, blood glucose management, and other characteristics, as evidenced by the data's notable variability across all of these metrics. There are noticeable variations in blood sugar, hemoglobin A1c (HbA1c), low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and cholesterol levels; these areas may require targeted therapies.

Section 2: Level of Satisfaction

Statement | Very Satisfied | Somewhat Satisfied

The data emphasizes several aspects of patient satisfaction and possible areas of improvement in diabetes treatment. The duration of their treatment

makes most patients happy; 27.3% are totally content and 27.0% are rather satisfied. Though most people find treatment plans to be acceptable, some people could benefit from more optimization since only a small

fraction (9.6%) expressed dissatisfaction. Test-related operations could use some work since 6.8% of patients are unhappy with the allowed time for testing and 37% of them are satisfied.

Figure 2: Level of Satisfaction

Compared to other areas, blood sugar monitoring appears to divide opinions the most. Twenty to five percent of patients are completely satisfied, whereas the other half are not, indicating a clear need for improvement in this procedure. Even though 46.2% of patients are happy with their current procedures, 11.9% are not, which suggests that there is a problem that is either too complicated or ineffective.

It goes without saying that family support and dietary flexibility must be addressed. 48.1% of people who have tried multiple diets are satisfied with their choices,

compared to 8.1% who are not. It is evident that improved counseling and support systems are required, as 17.7% of families express dissatisfaction with the way their loved one manages the condition. The need to improve patient education programs to support self-management is underscored by the existence of comparable gaps in diabetes education, with 23.9% of respondents expressing dissatisfaction.

Given that 60.5% of respondents say they are happy with their sleep, it is clear that targeted treatments are needed to address sleep-related problems, even

though 10.6% of people are not satisfied with their sleep. High levels of satisfaction (65.9% for social connections and 61.9% for productivity) indicate strengths, but ongoing support is needed to help maintain these exceptional accomplishments.

We see a mixed bag of results when it comes to self-perception and workout happiness. 12.7% of people are unhappy with their body image, despite 42.3% being satisfied; therefore, they may require assistance to increase their self-esteem. There is opportunity for improvement to address the 14.5% dissatisfaction, even though the majority of people (47.3%) are content with their exercise regimens.

With 44.4% of respondents expressing satisfaction with leisure activities and 48.6% with overall life satisfaction, these areas are doing well. The majority of diabetics appear to have a positive outlook on life, but if we could

only find answers for the small problems that make them unhappy, their quality of life could be even better.

Section 3: Level of Impact

Statement / Never / Very Rarely

As the table shows, persons with diabetes have physical, psychological, and social as well as practical challenges in their daily lives. About half of individuals who answered the survey stated their diabetes treatment caused "a little bit" of discomfort; about a third said they felt this "sometimes." 47.8% of respondents replied "sometimes," implying that their illness greatly influences their social interactions, when asked how frequently they feel ashamed in public. Of all diabetics, around half (52.7%) say their blood sugar "sometimes" drops. Another common complaint is 59.7% percent of diabetics stating they feel physically tired "sometimes".

Figure 3: Level of Impact

Diabetics exhibit a range of levels of self-satisfaction. Notably, 15.3% of respondents say they are "always satisfied," despite 53.2% saying they are "sometimes satisfied." According to 61.8% of diabetics, "not at least," meaning that their condition does not impair their ability to drive or operate machinery. In fact, 73.8% of people feel they "a little bit" need to explain their illness to others, and 48.1% of people with diabetes feel the same way.

Dealing with people could also be challenging; for instance, 150 respondents claimed they felt "a little bit" annoyed when others mentioned they couldn't eat sweets, and 142 respondents stated the same thing "sometimes." Frequent bathroom needs are another common diabetes symptom; 36.9% of diabetics say they experience this "sometimes." Managing one's health while negotiating societal expectations is difficult; 37.1% of respondents said they ate unsuitable meals "sometimes" instead of revealing their circumstances. All taken together, the figures reveal that diabetes affects people's life in somewhat varied ways.

Section 4: Anxiety Related to Diabetes

Statement | Never | Very Rarely

The table shows the degrees of concern diabetic persons have about numerous facets of their life.

Table 6: Anxiety Related to Diabetes

Do you worry about your ability to take a vacation?	not at all	25.2
	little bit	39.7
	sometimes	31.2
	usually	2.6
	always	.5
Do you often worry about losing consciousness?	not at all	15.3
	little bit	36.6
	sometimes	36.1
	usually	7.8
	always	3.4
Do you worry about body shape changes caused by diabetes?	not at all	18.2
	little bit	31.4
	sometimes	40.0
	usually	8.3
	always	1.3
Do you worry about future complications of diabetes?	not at all	11.4
	little bit	29.1
	sometimes	48.1
	usually	5.2
	always	5.5

About forty percent are anxious "a little bit," and thirty-two percent are worried "sometimes" about their ability to afford a vacation." < With 36.6% feeling "a little bit" and 36.1% experiencing it "sometimes," there is a general worry about possible emergencies and

diabetes-related consciousness loss. The way diabetes can change one's body form is another often shared issue; 40.0% of respondents "sometimes" and 31.4% "a little bit."

This implies that for many people, their appearance mentally and emotionally counts greatly. With over a third (29.1%), admitting they worry "a little bit," over half of all diabetics (48.1%) said they worry about the possible implications of the condition "sometimes." These results draw attention to the ongoing worries among diabetics in management about appearance, health, and lifestyle. These issues capture their ongoing challenges in daily life as well as in future planning.

Conclusion

Finally, the findings highlight the need to give Type 2 Diabetes top priority in studies and therapies. One cannot stress the need to meet the requirements of people with long-term diabetes as well as newly diagnosed patients. By leveraging the great frequency of family history, community education and preventative programs could also significantly lower the future prevalence of diabetes.

Conflict of Interest Statement

The authors state that they have no conflict of interest.

Funding

No funding for this work was received.

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